

THE ROLE OF SELF-ESTEEM IN THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF FOSTER YOUTH IN HIGHER EDUCATION

by

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Abstract

An overwhelming majority of current and former foster youth have a desire to obtain a college degree, however, less than 10% successfully earn a baccalaureate degree. To improve educational outcomes for foster youth college students, it is crucial to understand how psychological factors affect their academic success. The purpose of this research is to explore the relationship between self-esteem and the academic achievement of foster youth in higher education. It is hypothesized that higher levels of self-esteem will correlate with increased grade point averages among foster youth students. This study is a secondary data analysis of the *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study*. In the current study, 101 participants were interviewed following completion of their second academic year at a four-year university. Data related to grade point averages, number of courses passed and failed in the past year, and perceived self-esteem were collected. A significant positive correlation between self-esteem and grade point average was found. Multiple linear regression indicated self-esteem to be a significant predictor of increased grade point average among foster youth college students attending a four-year university. This research will have implications for foster youth students attending a post-secondary institution, as well as campus support services providers and administrators.

Introduction

Both current and former foster youth encounter a surplus of difficulties throughout and following their years in the foster care system. The difficulties these youth face undoubtedly impact numerous aspects of their lives, most notably affecting their academic performance throughout all stages of their educational journey. Research indicates that there are significant disparities in the academic performance of both current and former foster youth as compared to their non-foster care counterparts (Clemens et al., 2018). In order to alter this reality, it is crucial to gain an understanding of what barriers are prohibiting the success of foster youth in academic settings. With significant research having already been conducted on situational factors, it is necessary to study the psychological factors affecting the academic performance of foster youth.

Research throughout the years has found that academic achievement among foster youth students is significantly lower, and at times practically non-existent when compared to those never in the foster care system (Burns et al., 2022). Some situational factors causing this have been studied and revealed that disciplinary referrals, placement instability, and behavioral problems are all factors contributing to poor academic success among both current and former foster youth (Somers et al., 2020). However, there is a lack of research exploring how psychological factors, most notably the factor of self-esteem, affect a foster youth's overall academic performance (Gypen et al., 2017). To aid these youth in becoming more academically successful, there needs to be an understanding of the role self-esteem has on their academic achievement. Therefore, for there to be any improvement in low academic achievement among foster youth, there is a need for research exploring how psychological factors, such as self-esteem, may be prohibiting an adolescent's academic success.

Foster youth have been found to experience a decrease, and often a loss, of self-esteem as a result of their time in the foster care system (Thompson et al., 2016). Plagued with questions such as “Why doesn’t anybody want me?” or “What’s wrong with me?”, it should come as no surprise that these youth experience a devaluation of self and, therefore, exhibit low levels of self-esteem. Despite already having research focusing on the self-esteem levels of youth, there is a lack of knowledge on the correlation between foster youths’ self-reported levels of self-esteem and their academic performance. Thus, the proceeding research strives to answer the question of, what relationship exists between self-esteem and the academic achievement of former and current foster youth in higher education? It is hypothesized that former and current foster youth with higher levels of self-esteem will also have higher levels of academic achievement. Consequently, there will be a relatively strong positive correlation between the self-esteem of an adolescent formerly in the foster care system and their academic performance during their time at a four-year college or university.

To answer this research question, a secondary data analysis of the *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study* was conducted (Hogan, 2015). The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale was administered to former and current foster youth who were enrolled in post-secondary education at four-year universities. The grades and grade point averages of the youth were also collected to determine the relationship between their self-esteem and academic performance. A multiple linear regression was used to examine the predictive quality of self-esteem on academic achievement, when controlling for such variables as gender, ethnicity, and length of time in foster care.

Ultimately, both current and former foster youth are confronted with a variety of barriers including but not limited to behavioral difficulties, disciplinary referrals, and placement

instability, all of which impact numerous aspects of their life, but most notably their academic performance. Self-esteem has also been found to influence the life of a child or adolescent who was or is in the foster care system. What has not been found, however, is a relationship between the youths' reported levels of self-esteem and their academic performance. Thus, the research that proceeds is focused on determining if there is a relationship between the two and, if there is, what type of relationship is present. Considering the significant amount of foster youth who openly express their desire to attend and succeed at a four-year university (Rios & Rocco, 2014), it is important to examine if low levels of self-esteem are interfering with that goal in any way. With the identification of self-esteem's role in the academic performance, or lack thereof, of former and current foster youth, progress can be made to promote the academic success of these youth, especially during their time in post-secondary education.

Literature Review

Social Cognitive Theory

When considering the relationship between the self-esteem and academic performance of foster youth, one theory applicable to this research is Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory. One tenet of this theory explains how people's confidence in their own worth and capabilities, also referred to as their self-esteem, affect their actions and whether or not they produce desired outcomes (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). In other words, if foster youth do not believe in themselves and their ability to be successful in their classes then they will likely dwell on the difficulty of their classes, put in minimal and insufficient effort, and ultimately fail. On the contrary, it is implied that foster youth with high self-esteem believe that they can do what is necessary to pass their classes leading to them being successful. The self-esteem these individuals have affects their confidence in whether they can employ the skills necessary to meet

the demands of their classes and be successful overall in their education. A significant note about social cognitive theory and foster youth is that these youths undoubtedly have been confronted with adverse conditions and uncertain outcomes (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Stajkovic and Luthans (1998) found that youth who exhibit high self-esteem utilize that belief in themselves to counteract the adverse conditions they have been faced with and persevere through all of the uncertainty. Thus, it is evident that Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory is most applicable to the research at hand investigating the correlation between the self-esteem and academic performance of foster youth in higher education.

Review of Past Research

When examining the academic performance of youth in the foster care system as well as those who have aged out of it, it is evident that the overall performance is low. Foster youth have been found to perform significantly poorer academically than their non-foster-care youth counterparts (Somers et al., 2020). Rios and Rocco (2014) found that despite more than half of former foster youth having the desire to attend college, less than a quarter of them actually do. In addition, less than 10% of youth previously in foster care succeed in graduating and obtaining a college degree (Rios & Rocco, 2014). Regardless of the fact that a significant majority of these youth aspire to be academically successful, the amount of those who actually succeed does not accurately reflect the amount of those who wish to. In order to make a substantial change and increase the amount of foster youth who attend and succeed at a university, there needs to be clarity on what has to be changed to aid these youth. Thus, this literature review examines both the situational and psychological factors that have repercussions on the foster child's future in postsecondary education, which ultimately affects a majority of their additional future outcomes.

Disciplinary Referrals

Disciplinary referrals cover a group of factors that have a substantial influence on the academic success of foster youth. These referrals include school detentions, suspensions, and expulsions (Somers et al., 2020). Although children from varying familial backgrounds are disciplined, O'Higgins et al. (2017) report that foster youth have higher rates of grade repeats, absences, suspensions, and expulsions. All three of these disciplinary actions result in foster youth having difficulty completing their primary and secondary education degrees (Unrau et al., 2012). With these youth consistently being disciplined by their teachers and supervisors at school, their attention is directed more towards that than it is their studies. Foster youths' lack of focus and emphasis on their own education during primary and secondary school results in it being highly unlikely that the adolescent will pursue and secure a college degree seeing as there was already a substantial struggle with completing K-12. Therefore, disciplinary referrals become standard for the child and are sometimes sought out by them considering it may be the only way they receive attention from an adult or authority figure (Somers et al., 2020). With the rest of their environment consistently changing, disciplinary referrals may be something they cling to despite the fact that it is prohibiting their education and academic success.

Behavioral Difficulties

Often resulting in these youth beginning to act out and receive disciplinary referrals, behavioral difficulties are another factor that places foster children at risk for academic difficulties (O'Higgins, 2017). These youth have more likely than not witnessed or experienced abuse, neglect, or violence which leads to them having emotional and behavioral difficulties including, but not limited to, depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (Somers et al., 2020). The behaviors that these youth exhibit are often learned and repeated based on the

behaviors that they witness or experience from parents or guardians. As a result of their past experiences, the primary emotion that drives foster youths' behavior is anger. The anger can stem from a variety of places, and it leads these youth to partake in poor behaviors which often can result in them being suspended or expelled (Rios & Rocco, 2014). Distracted by the constant inner battle and urge to act on their emotions, foster youth students are not focusing on their education, which results in them being unsuccessful in their K-12 education and therefore less likely to pursue a degree in higher education.

Placement Instability

The most notable factor influencing academic success, or lack thereof, among foster youth is placement instability. Placement refers to the constant change in housing situations for these youth, which also signifies a constant change in school situations and settings (Clemens et al., 2018). With two immense aspects of the child's life being altered regularly, it is challenging for the child to adjust to both of these changes (Clemens et al., 2018). Prioritizing the adjustment to their new housing placement, foster youth generally fail at adjusting to the numerous schools they are being transferred to and from (O'Higgins et al., 2017). On average, youth move to a new foster care placement up to three times per year, which means that the child is also switching schools up to three times a year (Kirk & Day, 2011). This shift in schools in the middle of the school year results in a variation in the content taught, the teaching styles used, and the school's culture which alters the academic growth of the foster youth student (Clemens et al., 2018). Placement instability is deterring foster youth from succeeding academically as at the end of each school year, they do not expand their knowledge or education as much as they are expected to. Students who change schools are at high risk for grade retention with an estimated 13% of 302 foster youth repeating at least one grade (Sullivan et al., 2010). Consequently, each year

these students continue to fall further behind the academic level at which they should be functioning, therefore widening the academic success gap, and narrowing their likelihood of attending a four-year college and successfully graduating from it with a degree.

Desire to Attend College

As previously mentioned, the academic performance of foster youth during primary and secondary school is severely impacted by the barriers these youth encounter including placement instability, disciplinary referrals, and behavioral difficulties. Despite the usual poor performance of these youth in school, a significant majority of them have the desire to attend college and obtain a post-secondary educational degree. However, foster youth are not enrolling and succeeding in college at the same rates as their non-foster youth counterparts (Frerer et al., 2013). Kirk and Day (2011) found that over 70% of 15 to 19-year-old foster youth have the desire to attend college and 19% even report a desire to attend graduate school. Despite the overwhelming amount of foster youth who have the desire to attend both undergraduate and graduate school, the reported number of those who actually pursue a four-year degree is alarmingly low. At the age of 19, it was found that only 18% of foster youth are actually pursuing a degree at a four-year college or university (Kirk & Day, 2011). Thus, more than half of former foster youth have the desire to acquire a college degree (Rios & Rocco, 2014); however, it is rare that they are actually successful in enrolling in a four-year program and graduating with said degree. Despite successfully completing high school and having high aspirations to attend college, foster youth are one of the most underrepresented groups among college-going populations. Therefore, it is evident that there are factors contributing to their lack of success, which is ultimately also impacting their potential to be successful in varying domains of their life in the future.

Mental Health

When studying what could be prohibiting the academic success of current and former foster youth enrolled at a four-year university, one of the most detectable factors is mental health. These youth undoubtedly experience a variety of mental health issues as they are consistently forced to leave their familiar homes and environments and enter unfamiliar ones (Hogan, 2018), which can be mentally taxing. Additionally, the pressure of performing well in their post-secondary education coupled with their history of traumatic life events results in poor psychological well-being among these foster youth (Hogan, 2018). Thus, it is not surprising that foster youth who are already struggling with their mental health prior to entering a four-year university, experience increased mental health issues as a result of the transitional period and their first year. What is also apparent among foster youth is that they are less likely to seek help for their mental health issues due to feelings of alienation and a stigma against them for being foster youth (Hogan, 2018). Not seeking help exacerbates the issue as their mental health continues to suffer throughout their years at the university which ultimately affects their academic performance. Therefore, the mental health of foster youth in higher education is an important factor to take into account as their psychological well-being ultimately impacts their academic performance.

Self-Esteem

Self-esteem is an additional barrier that current and former foster youth encounter, which also has an effect on a variety of other aspects of the youth's life. Self-esteem is defined as the feelings an individual has in regard to their self-worth, liking, and acceptance (Paradise & Kernis, 2002). The foster care system takes a toll on the self-esteem of foster children, which results in their self-esteem being lower than that of children not in the foster care system

(Farineau et al., 2011). Placement instability, one of the barriers previously mentioned, has an effect on the self-esteem of foster youth because the inconsistency of homes and loving parents means the child does not believe they have self-worth. With each new placement comes the loss of family members, friends, and the neighborhoods in which they lived, causing their self-esteem to diminish as they feel unwanted from their previous caregivers (Farineau et al., 2011). These youth believe that if they had self-worth, then they would be in a loving home and there would be stability in their life. This lack of self-esteem has detrimental effects on the youth's life as they are more likely to be involved in criminal behavior, have poorer mental and physical health, lower economic well-being, and display aggressive behaviors (Thompson et al., 2016). It is evident that the lack of self-esteem in these youth is extremely impactful in a variety of aspects of their life and another aspect worth noting is the impact it has on their academic performance.

As previously mentioned, most foster youth aspire to receive a post-secondary education, however, the expectations they have of themselves can impact their performance levels during primary and secondary education and prohibit them from pursuing that post-secondary education. Boxer et al. (2011) found that the student's grades, academic participation, and motivational levels during K-12 are impacted by their expectations and view of themselves. Therefore, self-esteem does directly impact the academic performance of these youth in primary and secondary schools as students who believe they can do well in school, or who have higher self-esteem, are more likely to do so than those who have lower self-esteem (Boxer et al., 2011). Foster youth who have been found to be academically successful during their high school years often link their academic performance to their self-esteem. It was reported that some foster youth will maintain a focus on their academics in K-12 as a way to repair their self-esteem (Neal, 2017). From their perspective, it is believed that there will be a significant boost in their self-

esteem, and possibly a repair of it, so long as they perform well academically. Hence, the foster youth interested in repairing their self-esteem perform so well academically that they manage to get into a four-year college or university. What is not clear is whether the academic performance of foster youth is influenced by their self-esteem or if it is the other way around. Thus, the proceeding research strives to clarify whether or not the academic performance of these youth is hinged upon their self-esteem in order to promote more successful completion of post-secondary education among them.

Importance of Academic Success

There are a handful of factors that influence the academic success of foster youth, which ultimately influence numerous aspects of the youth's life and future. The poorer educational outcomes these children face is an indication of poorer success later in life for these youth beginning with a decreased likelihood of pursuing and obtaining a post-secondary degree (Gypen et al., 2015). The absence of academic success results in fewer employment opportunities, lower-paying jobs, poorer health, and increased participation in criminal activity (Somers et al., 2020). Academic success translates to life success as individuals who perform well academically and get degrees, specifically degrees from a college or university, are given more advantages in housing stability, employment opportunities, and earning potential (Clemens et al., 2018). It is evident that the situational factors previously mentioned hold the weight of not only affecting the academic success of these youth but also affecting their future opportunities. Therefore, after already understanding how situational factors affect the academic performance of foster youth, it is crucial to now discover how the specific psychological factor of self-esteem hinders the academic and overall future success of these former foster youths as well.

Positive Social Change

It is evident that significant disparities are present in the academic performance of both current and former foster youth compared to the rest of the general population. An answer must be provided to the question of what correlation lies between former foster youth's reports of their own self-esteem and their grades during their educational career at a four-year university.

Gathering data on what role self-esteem plays in the academic success of college students previously in foster care is imperative to determine what action needs to be taken in order to promote the academic success of these students. Upon identifying the correlation, work can begin on breaking down what self-esteem is like for these youth so that they may be provided with the resources and supports necessary to then boost their self-esteem and be as successful as their counterparts. The results of this research will not only contribute to an increase in attention on the self-esteem levels of former foster youth but will also grant them access to better resources, which will then boost their overall academic performance. With statistics indicating that more than 70% of foster youth desire to attend college (Rios & Rocco, 2014), it is time to make that desire a reality and ensure that the number of those who actually receive degrees from a four-year university is equivalent to those who have the desire to graduate from college.

Promoting increased graduation rates for foster youth students will effect positive social change for these individuals, as well as the families they live with and the communities they work in.

Summary

Ultimately, there has been a significant amount of research completed revealing what factors limit and prevent both current and former foster youth from succeeding academically, especially as it pertains to pursuing and obtaining a degree from a four-year college or university. It has been found that disciplinary referrals, behavioral difficulties, and housing instability are

the most prominent situational factors inhibiting academic success among foster youth during their years in primary and secondary education (Somers et al., 2020). Self-esteem is another prominent issue among foster youth (Gypen et al., 2017), however, there is a lack of research investigating the correlation between the youth's post-secondary academic performance and their self-esteem. In order to increase the percentage of foster youth who attend and successfully graduate from college, there needs to be complete clarity on if self-esteem is a relevant factor impacting the academic success of these youth. With research highlighting the factors preventing foster youth from pursuing a four-year degree, there is a need for additional research on the potential correlation between the student's self-esteem and their ability to successfully graduate from a university. Hence, progress can be made to promote the success of these youth in obtaining a four-year university degree only after discovering what exactly is prohibiting that progress.

Methodology

Research Design

Original Study

The original *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study* (Hogan, 2015) was a longitudinal panel study of current and former foster youth transitioning to adulthood through higher education. There was a total of 123 participants from across the Southern California area interviewed over a 3-year period by the principal investigator and graduate student researchers from the Department of Social Work at Cal State Fullerton. All study participants were interviewed prior to beginning their post-secondary education at a four-year university and then at 12- and 24-month follow-ups (following completion of their first and second academic years). The original study explored relationships between a number of variables, including social capital,

social support, physical and mental health, substance use, spirituality, victimization, and foster care experience.

Current Study

The current study is a secondary data analysis of the original *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study* (Hogan, 2015). This is a cross-sectional study focusing exclusively on data from the 24-month follow-up. Using a correlational survey design, the current study explored the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement among former and current foster youth on a four-year campus.

Sampling

Original Study

The participants from the original study were chosen using convenience sampling. All eligible foster youth were recruited over the course of three summers from a variety of child welfare and educational agencies and organizations in Southern California. California State University at Fullerton's Guardian Scholars program; California State Polytechnic University, Pomona's Renaissance Scholars program; Orangewood Children's Foundation (Santa Ana); United Friends of the Children (Los Angeles); and Promises to Kids (San Diego) were included in the list of community and institutional partners. All potential study participants were identified by each agency or organization's list of clients and were given information on an opportunity to participate in a research project that could benefit former foster youth. The sample size for Wave 1 of the original study was 123 participants with 114 interviews conducted at the 12-month follow-up (7% attrition) and 101 interviews conducted at the 24-month follow-up (18% attrition).

Current Study

The current study included the entire original sample of all 101 participants who completed the 24-month follow-up interview after the end of their second academic year at a four-year university. In this sample, 23 study participants entered the four-year university as junior college transfers; 78 study participants entered as freshman (Hogan, 2015).

Measures

Variables

Independent Variables. The primary independent variable in this study is self-esteem. Self-esteem refers to the feelings an individual has of their own self-worth, liking, and acceptance (Paradise & Kernis, 2002). This variable was measured using Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale where participants had to indicate the extent they agree or disagree with statements that dealt with their general feelings about themselves. These statements covered their overall satisfaction with themselves (e.g., if they're good at all, if they possess good qualities), if they have a positive attitude towards themselves (e.g., do they feel useless, are they a person of worth), if they feel they are a failure (e.g., do they do things as well as others, do they have much to be proud of), and if they believe they could have more respect for themselves.

Additional independent variables present in this study included demographic variables, such as age, ethnicity, and gender. Age is a continuous variable measured in years, ethnicity is a categorical variable with four categories (African American, Caucasian, Hispanic, Other); and gender is a dichotomous variable with the options being either male or female. Additionally, there is the educational level (Sophomore, Junior, Senior, Graduate) and employment status (Yes, No) of the individual. A study participant's previous foster care experience, including the

number of years in the system, number of placements, and emancipation status (Yes, No), was gathered. Using self-report, perceived physical health was also measured.

Dependent Variable. The dependent variable in this study is the educational outcomes of current and former foster youth. The academic achievement of participants was measured through their grade point average (0.0-4.0 scale). Additional categorical variables were constructed for passage of all courses taken in the previous year (Yes, No) and number of courses failed in the past year (No courses failed, 1 course, 2 courses, 3 or more courses).

Instrumentation

Self-esteem was measured using Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale, a 10-item questionnaire. In the original *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study*, items in the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale were expanded from a 4-point to a 5-point Likert scale format for increased sensitivity (Hogan, 2015). The categories on the 5-point Likert scale format ranged from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The scores ranged from 10 to 50 points, with higher scores indicating higher self-esteem. The normal range of cumulative scores for a 5-point Likert scale format is 31 to 43, with scores below 31 indicating low self-esteem. Cronbach's alpha for Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale was .905, indicating that the scale has very good internal consistency (i.e., reliability).

Data Collection

The original *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study* consisted of three panels of foster youth students totaling 123 participants interviewed over a 48-month period. The first interview was conducted right before the youth started at a four-year university, followed by a 12-month follow-up at the end of their first academic year on a four-year campus and a 24-month follow-up at the end of their second academic year on a four-year campus (Hogan, 2015). The

interviews were administered by the research team, which included the principal investigator and graduate student researchers who were trained to administer the questionnaire in order to ensure inter-rater reliability. The interviews were conducted primarily in the Department of Social Work offices on the main campus of Cal State Fullerton, as well as at the participants' homes. For study participants who were unable to come to any of the locations, their interviews were conducted at community locations, such as a coffee shop or library. Each interview took approximately 60-90 minutes per participant.

In the original study, all participants were interviewed once a year, from 2011 to 2015, between the months of June and October. The research team contacted all participants bi-annually, by telephone or email, to reinforce their relationship and update contact information if applicable. Password-protected personal computers in the principal investigator's office kept all of the data collected.

Human Subjects

All information from the *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study* was kept confidential (Hogan, 2015). Participants were required to sign an informed consent form after being briefed on the intentions, goals, procedures, risks, and benefits of the research study. There were minimal harms and risks to study participants. The results from the study were intended to benefit transitional age foster youth. All participation in this study was voluntary and participants could withdraw at any time without being penalized. There were no conflicts of interest between the principal investigator and any of the participating agencies or study participants. All study participants were provided with \$50 cash after the completion of each annual interview. California State University at Fullerton (HSR-11-0217) and California State Polytechnic University at Pomona (Protocol No. 11-152) granted Institutional Review Board approval.

Statistical Analysis

In the current study, descriptive statistical tests were used to analyze the basic features of the study sample, such as the mean age and grade point average of the participants or the percentage breakdown of the participant's ethnicity. Inferential statistical tests were utilized to examine the relationship between the self-esteem of the foster youth students and their academic achievement. Multiple linear regression was used to predict the grade point averages of each of the participants based on their level of self-esteem, when controlling for such factors as age, gender, and the total amount of time in foster care over lifetime.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

The sample from the current study was collected from the *Foster Youth in Higher Education Study* (Hogan, 2015). There was a total of 101 participants for the third-wave of interviews, with their mean age being 21.42 years ($SD = 2.23$). The gender of caregivers in the study was 67.3% female and 32.7% male. The racial and ethnic identity reported was 22.8% African American, 18.8% Caucasian, 38.6% Hispanic, and 19.8% other race. The mean annual income among participants was \$14,941 ($SD = \$12,093$). It was reported that 22.8% of participants transferred from a junior college to a four-year university, while 77.2% of participants went straight to a four-year university after high school.

The average number of foster care placements the participants had in a lifetime was 3.95 ($SD = 4.28$). As for the amount of time spent in foster care, the mean number of months was 85.13 ($SD = 64.11$). The mean grade point average among the participants during their time in college was 2.98 ($SD = 0.47$). Using Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale, the average self-esteem score among participants was 42.35 ($SD = 6.70$). In regard to foster care experience, the mean

Table 1

Study Participant Characteristics (N = 101)

Characteristic	<i>f</i> (%)	Characteristic	Mean (<i>SD</i>)
Gender		Age (years)	21.42 (2.23)
Male	33 (32.7)	Annual income	\$14,941 (\$12,093)
Female	68 (67.3)	Foster care experience	
Ethnicity		Age at first placement (years)	9.99 (5.40)
African American	23 (22.8)	Number of placements (lifetime)	3.95 (4.28)
Caucasian	19 (18.8)	Lifetime in foster care (months)	85.13 (64.11)
Hispanic	39 (38.6)	Grade point average (college)	2.98 (0.47)
Other	20 (19.8)	Self-esteem	42.35 (6.70)
Junior college transfer	23 (22.8)		

age of participants at the time of their initial placement in foster care was 9.99 years ($SD = 5.40$).

Refer to Table 1 for a summary of demographic information.

Inferential Analysis

Correlation

The relationship between self-esteem and grade point average was examined using a Pearson's correlation analysis. The results indicated a positive and statistically significant association between self-esteem and grade point average, $r(99) = .226, p = .011$. The strength of the correlation was moderate. The greater the level of self-esteem, the higher the grade point average among foster youth students.

Multiple Linear Regression

A multiple linear regression was performed to predict a study participant's grade point average based on their age, gender, employment status, total time in foster care, and self-esteem. A significant regression equation was found ($F(5, 95) = 6.226, p < .001$), with an R^2 of .25. This indicates that 25% of the variance in grade point average was explained by the regression model. A study participant's predicted grade point average was equal to $1.447 + .039(\text{age}) - .109(\text{male}) + .287(\text{employed}) - .002(\text{months in foster care}) + .017(\text{self-esteem})$. Older, employed foster youth students with less lifetime in foster care had higher grade point averages, when compared to other study participants ($p < .05$); foster youth students with higher self-esteem also had significantly higher grade point averages than foster youth students with lower self-esteem ($p = .009$). In this model, gender was not a significant predictor of grade point average among the study participants ($p = .238$).

Table 2

Regression Model for Grade Point Average

Predictor	<i>B</i>	95% <i>CI</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	1.45	[.495, 2.40]	0.48		3.02	.003
Self-esteem	.017	[.004, .030]	.006	.241	2.65	.009
Age	.039	[.001, .077]	.019	.183	2.01	.047
Gender	-.109	[-.291, -.073]	.092	-.109	-1.19	.238
Employment status	.287	[.115, .459]	.087	.298	3.31	.001
Total time in foster care	-.002	[-.003, .001]	.001	-.250	-2.76	.007

Reference groups: Female, Not employed

Discussion

Significance of the Findings

The results of this research study reveal that there is indeed a relationship between the self-esteem of foster youth students enrolled at a post-secondary institution and their academic achievement. As hypothesized, students who had a higher self-esteem score had a higher grade point average, while the students who had a lower self-esteem score had a lower grade point average. Often doubting their own capabilities, foster youth experience a devaluation of self as a result of their experiences with the foster care system. This doubt proceeds throughout their post-secondary education and its repercussions on their academic performance are evident, as seen in the results of this study. The positive correlation between self-esteem and grade point average demonstrates how the value the foster youth students place on themselves and their success ultimately affects how they perform academically.

Previous research on the impact of self-esteem aligns with the results that were found in this research study. Boxer et al. (2011) found that self-esteem does have a direct impact on the academic performance of these youth during their primary and secondary education. This coincides with this research study as it was shown that self-esteem has a direct correlation to the academic performance of foster youth during their time at a post-secondary institution. Prior research has also proven that elementary and secondary foster youth students who believe they can do well, or who are exhibiting higher self-esteem levels, are more likely to do so than those who report low self-esteem levels (Boxer et al., 2011). This previous research confirms that self-esteem levels do not solely impact the academic performance of foster youth during post-secondary education, but rather the correlation between the two can be drawn beginning with the youth's first school experience in kindergarten. Therefore, the results presented in this research

study should have been anticipated based on prior research studying the effect self-esteem has on the K-12 education of foster youth students.

As the results of this research study support the initial hypothesis, Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory can still be considered applicable when examining the relationship between the two variables. Stajkovic and Luthans (1998) determined that the actions of the youth are determined by the confidence they have about their worth and capabilities. In regard to this study, the actions refer to the student's academic performance and their worth and capabilities is in reference to their self-esteem. This theory emphasizes that foster youth with high self-esteem have faith in themselves and their ability to pass their classes, leading them down the path of academic success. As mentioned previously, these youth have gone through the unthinkable and in spite of this, they are utilizing the belief they have in themselves to counteract the adverse conditions they have faced to persevere and be successful (Stajkovic and Luthans, 1998). This provides an explanation as to why, in this study, the foster youth who were reported as having high self-esteem performed well academically. Conclusively, the results that were presented in this research study can be interpreted utilizing Bandura's social cognitive theory.

Strengths and Limitations

This study has potential limitations. The topic of this study was determined based on pre-existing data from the primary research study. Contrary to primary research, this study's research question was conceptualized following an examination of the original data. As all of the data was collected prior to the beginning of this study, this research was constrained by the limits of the original data. This is another limitation because all of the selection criteria for participants and methodology were chosen based on the needs of the original study rather than the current study. Alongside this, an additional limitation is selection bias. With a small sample size of students

from only Southern California, it is difficult to determine if the results are generalizable to foster youth nationwide, or if it only pertains to those from this specific region. In regard to strengths, the usage of Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale ensured that the reported self-esteem of these youth was reliable and valid.

Implications for Future Research

Given the limitations, one implication for future research would be to collect new data to ensure that future studies are not also constrained by the limits of the data from the original study. The utilization of a larger sample size would be another potential implication for future research. With a relatively larger sample size, it can be determined if the significantly positive correlation found between self-esteem and academic achievement is applicable to foster youth outside of the Southern California region as well. In addition to a larger sample size, a different group of foster youth could also be surveyed to establish if there is a relationship between self-esteem and the academic performance of all foster youth. Another implication for future research is to examine the impact of support systems on the self-esteem of foster youth. Future research could specifically explore if the amount of support systems an individual has boosts their self-esteem and if that is ultimately correlated to their academic performance. Ultimately, there are numerous different directions that future research could take including the collection of new data, the usage of a larger sample size, and the examination of the effect of additional outside factors on the self-esteem and academic performance of foster youth.

Implications for Child and Adolescent Studies

This research has implications for foster youth students attending a post-secondary institution. As it has been determined that there is a correlation between the self-esteem of foster youth and their academic performance, progress can be made to boost the youth's self-esteem.

The foster youth students struggling at their post-secondary institution are also able to reflect on their journey and determine if their self-esteem is a contributing factor to their struggle. With this knowledge, these youth can put more effort into taking the necessary steps to increase their self-esteem. This research also has implications for campus support services providers and administrators. These individuals will be able to not only provide but also promote services that foster youth students can take advantage of to improve their self-esteem such as counseling or advising. The providers and administrators may also offer support for the foster youth students, through mentorship or academic programs, that will help enhance their academic performance. Thus, this study has implications for the students as well as for the providers and administrators of the campus support services provided at these post-secondary institutions.

Conclusion

With the knowledge that an overwhelming majority of foster youth are interested in obtaining a college degree, it was imperative to examine how self-esteem may be prohibiting them from achieving this. This research study determined that there is a relationship between the perceived self-esteem of foster youth enrolled at a post-secondary institution and their academic performance. The correlation between the two signifies that the self-esteem of foster youth is a factor impacting their academic success in higher education. Therefore, progress needs to be made to boost the self-esteem of these youth to ensure that their performance academically also sees a boost. In the meantime, campus support services providers and administrators can promote services that may support foster youth during their time at a post-secondary institution.

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